

Flow cytometry transport assay for SLC2A2 using HEK293 JumpIN TRex SLC2A2 WT-OE cells

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Assay description

A flow cytometry assay for the glucose transporter SLC2A2/GLUT2 was developed with a genetically-encoded biosensor for measuring free glucose, FLII12Pglu-700 μ d6 (Addgene #17866). This biosensor consists of the *E. Coli* glucose/galactose-binding protein MglB sandwiched between ECFP and Citrine-YFP. An increase in glucose concentration (dynamic range 0.05 – 11 mM) results in an increased FRET efficiency that can be observed by an increase in Citrine acceptor emission and a decrease in ECFP donor emission.

Assay protocol

The HEK293 JumpIN TRex SLC2A2 WT-OE cell line were cultured in high-glucose DMEM supplemented with 10% dialyzed FBS at 37 °C in a humidified incubator at 5% CO₂. Cells were subcultured three times per week or at ~90% confluency using Trypsin-EDTA and were regularly tested for mycoplasma infection. Two days prior to the assay, cells were split to 30-50% confluency in two T75 flasks. To one flask 1 μ g/mL doxycycline was added after 4-6h to allow for cell attachment. The following day, doxycycline was removed and cells were transfected with 10 μ g / T75 FLII12Pglu-700 μ d6 using Lipofectamine 2000 or 3000 according to the manufacturer's instructions. After one day, cells were starved for 2h in 10% dial. FBS/no-glucose DMEM. Then, cells were trypsinized, collected by centrifugation, resuspended in 5 mL / T75 10% dialyzed FBS/PBS, filtered through a cell strainer and diluted to a total volume of 18 mL / T75. 96w U-bottom plates were prepared containing 40 μ L of a 5X stock containing glucose and test compounds. Titrations of transport inhibitors were performed in presence of 1 mM glucose. 160 μ L of cell suspension was then added and incubated for 3-5 minutes before transferral to the LSR II Fortessa flow cytometer (BD Biosciences) HTS module. Doxycycline-induced cells and non-induced cells were always measured on the same 96 well plate. Cells were gated for expression in the FITC channel (Ex 488nm / Em 530/30), measured for FRET donor emission in the BV421 channel (Ex 405 nm / Em 450/50) and for FRET acceptor emission in the BV510 channel (Ex 405 nm / Em 525/50). Analysis was performed with the FlowJo10 software, cells were gated for live singlets (SSC-A vs FSC-A) and sensor expression (FITC positive). The FRET intensity ratio was derived by dividing the BV510 by the BV421 channel and was used for subsequent analysis, which is represented as mean FRET/CFP \pm 95% CI.

Additional information

According to resolute transcriptomics and proteomics data, wild-type HEK293 JumpIN TRex endogenously express SLC2A1 (<https://www.re-solute.eu/knowledgebase/gene/SLC2a1>) and SLC2A3 (<https://www.re-solute.eu/knowledgebase/gene/SLC2a3>). However, in wild-type HEK293 JumpIN TRex, negligible increases in free cytoplasmic glucose could be detected after glucose incubation (data not shown), indicating a low glucose uptake capacity and/or a high glycolytic capacity. The observed glucose uptake in the minus-doxycycline condition is therefore most likely due to leakiness of the TRex tetracycline-regulated expression system.

Target data

SLC	SLC2A2
Synonyms	GLUT2
SLC sub-family	SLC2 Facilitative GLUT transporter family
UniProt ID	P11168
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE02B8-R(HEK293 JumpIN TRex SLC2A2 WT-OE)

Assay data

<p>SLC2A2</p> <p>Legend: ● +doxy ■ -doxy</p>	Compound name (1)	Glucose
	PubChem CID	5793
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Gibco #A2494001
	Mode of action	Substrate
	EC50	710 μ M (+doxy), 1500 μ M (-doxy)
<p>SLC2A2 1 mM glc</p>	Compound name (2)	Bay-876
	PubChem CID	118191391
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Selleckchem, #S8452
	Mode of action	Inhibitor
	IC50	NA
<p>SLC2A2 1 mM glc</p>	Compound name (3)	Cytochalasin B
	PubChem CID	5311281
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Alfa Aesar, #J65342
	Mode of action	Inhibitor
	IC50	NA
<p>SLC2A2 1 mM glc</p>	Compound name (4)	WZB117
	PubChem CID	46830365
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Selleckchem, #S7927
	Mode of action	Inhibitor
	IC50	NA

Discussion

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).